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STATE OF THE ART RESEARCH

WJ/AWJ TECHNOLOGY IN AEROSPACE AND

AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS :

CAPABILITY OF CUTTING COMPLEX GEOMETRY PARTS

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Abstract

Since its discovery in mid 19th century, various papers regarding waterjet processes have been published, making this technology mature from the research standpoint. The goal of this review is to highlight advantages and issues of waterjet and abrasive waterjet basing on previous studies, as well as to provide statistical information about the quoted papers.

This research is focused on three main material classes (metallic alloys, composite materials, soft materials), with particular regard to aerospace- and automotive- related applications. One of the most interesting researches about cutting optimization and performances in milling complex 3D features is here summarized, considering also advanced and promising materials for the aerospace field such as CFRP/Ti stacks. An insight regarding sustainability-related processes as metallic alloys remanufacturing and tyres recycling is also provided. Finally, the paper also presents an overview on the current industrial employment of the aforementioned technologies, listing some companies and their most attracting solutions.

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1. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

1.1 Abrasive Water Jet Machining state of the art

Current advances in technology have caused an increasing demand for complex geometry parts with high quality requirements. AWJM is recognized as a powerful machining method for various materials (from stones going through metals and composites to soft materials), and to optimize the process a deep understanding of the working principle is needed.

Figure 1 – Sketch of an AWJ head

Considering actual technologies, in an AWJ head (Figure 1) water flows at high pressure through the primary orifice – where pressure is converted into kinetic energy – resulting in a high-speed water jet. When the jet reaches the mixing chamber, abrasive particles are fed with air; the resulting jet travels through the focuser where momentum is transferred to the abrasive grains [1]. The accelerated abrasive particles then impinge on the workpiece removing material by erosion:

- considering ductile materials, erosion occurs due to repeated plastic deformation;
- in brittle materials, erosion occurs due to crack propagation and chipping [2].

1. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

This mode of material removal gives AWJ many interesting properties:

1. Being a non-thermal method, no heat affected zone (called HAZ) is created, making machining feasible when no microstructure modification is allowed or when dealing with heat sensitive materials (since any thermal distortion is caused). In addition, no dangerous or polluting gases are generated, making the process way safer.
2. For the same reason, no burr is formed (a fact which is particularly appreciated in the aerospace field) and machining of high aspect ratio features (thin webs, grids etc.) [3] is feasible without issues related to material melting, even on thin parts.
3. The erosion mechanism is material independent, hence a wide range of materials with different thicknesses (up to 300 mm) can be processed with a negligible amount of lost material (favourable when machining high specific cost materials).
4. Thanks to the availability of different abrasives and facilities, parts with high difference in size can be machined.
5. Cutting forces are negligible, so workpiece clamping can be easily performed.
6. Water is the active cutting tool, so the cutting action itself would not provide tool wear. Clearly, the orifice and the focuser would be damaged while operating, but their replacing has a lower impact on the product cost with respect to conventional machining processes.
7. Waterjet is a multimode process therefore no tool change is needed within different processes, achieving lower setup times as well as the possibility to carry out roughing and finishing operations without the need of different facilities.

A comparison among the major non-conventional machining technologies is provided in Table 1.

Cutting Activity	AWJM	LBM	EDM	ECDM
Heated affected zone (HAZ)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Material Distortion	No	Yes	No	Yes
Tool Wear	No	No	Yes	Yes
Material Removal Rate (mm ³ /s)	Medium-slow (approx. ≤ 2)	Fast (approx. 2–3) for non-reflective materials only	Medium (approx.1–2)	Medium (approx.1–2)
Type of material	metals, composites, natural, electrically, non-conductive, non-reflective	metals, composites, natural, electrically, non-conductive, non-reflective surface	Only electrically conductive such as metals and composites	Only electrically conductive such as metals and composites
Material thickness (mm)	Ranging ≤ 304.8	Ranging ≤ 20	Ranging ≤ 304.8	Ranging ≤ 304.8
Type of shapes	Complex and complicated shapes	Complex and complicated shapes	Simple	Simple
Burr formation	Minimal	High	High	Minimal
Hazardous vapour	None	fumes, gases	CO & CH ₄	NaOH/NaNO ₃

Table 1 - Comparison between different non-conventional processes

Saracyakupoglu [4] showed a great impact comparison within different machining processes plotting accuracy vs. thickness, where it can be observed how AWJ achieves the best quality for the highest thickness (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Accuracy vs. thickness for different processes

However, AWJ is not inherently suitable for 3D machining: as a matter of fact abrasive grains still present considerable residual energy after cutting, hence they must be tamed in order to avoid machined surfaces damage. The most effective way to allow machining of 3D features is to use additional facilities like the A-Jet (complete software-controlled, 5-axis accessory which permits up to 60° of tilting in the vertical direction) or the Rotary Axis (rotary head which allows machining of axisymmetric features). In some cases, these devices allow to compensate the taper angle, which is a typical drawback of this process [3] [5].

1.2 Metallic alloys

AWJ shows good performances with all kinds of metallic alloys. Processing of standard alloys by means of AWJ is now common practice in industries and it has been deeply studied since the beginning of this process. In addition to this, new and interesting machining methods are being studied for what concerns manufacturing of advanced alloys and remanufacturing of worn-out components.

It is common to refer to an “advanced alloy” when dealing with an alloy capable of operating at a high fraction of its melting point. Key characteristics of an advanced alloy are excellent mechanical strength, resistance to thermal creep deformation, good surface stability, and resistance to corrosion or oxidation (provided by elements as aluminum and chromium). A deeper study of these materials (applications, machining, advantages and issues) will be approached in section 2.1.

1.3 Composite materials

Composite materials are becoming predominant over standard alloys in aerospace and high-performance automotive industries. According to Hale J. [6], using composite materials for aircraft structures allows weight reduction (-20%) and less routine maintenance (-35%); thanks to the favourable properties, usage of these kinds of material is steadily growing in aircraft manufacturing, as can be noticed by looking at the structural composition of the Airbus A350 XWB (composites account for 52% of the total structure) or at the Boeing 787 (composites account for 50% of the total structure). Many applications of composite materials can also be found in the automotive industry: back in 1972 Citroen introduced carbon fiber rims and throughout the years omnidirectional carbon fiber weaves became the standard materials for high-performance monocoque chassis and many other components [7].

The lightweight of composites, combined with their excellent mechanical properties, could be exploited in many applications, as long as a proper machining quality can be achieved. Applications of AWJ on composite materials will be analyzed in greater detail in section 2.2.

1.4 Soft materials

Effectiveness of WJ/AWJ on soft materials is well known and has been deeply investigated. The most important advantages are related to the fact that waterjet cutting is not a thermal process: soft materials, in fact, may be more susceptible to thermal damage, fire issues and dangerous gas generation than higher melting point materials. Focusing on automotive industry, waterjet cutting of soft materials is widely adopted in car interiors production. In addition to this, it was possible to find a certain number of interesting papers related to worn tyres dismantling by means of AWJ technology instead of using conventional mechanical techniques. All these aspects are discussed within section 2.3.

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The scope of this work is to analyze state of the art applications of AWJ machining on materials which are commonly used either in the automotive or in the aerospace field. A brief introduction on these kinds of materials and on AWJ as a machining method has already been provided, hence now the most interesting papers will be analyzed in order to deduce the main pros and cons of this non-conventional process.

2.1 Metallic alloys

These alloys are widely used in engineering structures where mass reduction or corrosion resistance is required. In particular, aluminum alloys are known for their corrosion resistance, ductility, conductivity, appearance, strength, and above all their light weight. The low weight of aluminum makes it especially useful for applications where weight saving is critical, like aerospace and automotive. In fact, when building their first airplane, the Wright Brothers knew that it was imperative to have a lightweight engine to power their plane. After having no luck finding a lightweight engine commercially available, the brothers decided to cast the engine block from an aluminum and copper alloy. In addition, cylinder block and crankcases are often cast made of aluminum alloys [8].

Figure 3 - Hardness vs. workpiece position in different processes

A typical issue when machining these kinds of materials is related to the HAZ caused by thermal processes, which deeply modifies the microstructure, leading to local increase of the hardness (Figure 3). This causes a general degradation of mechanical properties, especially in fatigue resistance as shown by Ulewicz R. and Nový F. [9]

2.1.1 *Remanufacturing of metallic alloys*

Having regard to global pollution issues, recycling is clearly a priority. O’Neil N. and Kabir A.S. [10] presented an impressive paper about remanufacturing of worn-out automotive engines, which has been proved to reduce CO₂ emissions by 80% when compared to the energy required to produce a new engine. Some of the main automotive manufacturers (such as Fiat, Ford, Peugeot etc.) currently use plasma transferred wire arc coating process to remanufacture engines. However, to improve the coating-substrate bond strength, it is necessary to deposit a really expensive Ni-Al pre-bond coat. The two authors managed to apply pulsed abrasive waterjet – which uses slugs of water to disintegrate the target material – to obtain a roughened surface profile, which has been used as a substitute of the pre-bond coat in order to make the process simpler, cheaper and more sustainable. All in all, this should promote usage of remanufacturing within automotive industries, making possible to achieve a way smaller carbon footprint.

The goal of their experiment is to optimize the obtained surface roughness in order to achieve a coating-substrate adhesion strength greater than 30 MPa, which is required for cylinder bore liners, on two different materials: Grey Cast Iron (GCI) and A380. The authors successfully demonstrated that surface roughness decreases with increasing transverse velocity for both materials (Figure 4, Figure 5). By measuring the required force to separate the coating from the roughened surface, they also managed to compute the bond strength (Figure 6) which resulted to be more than the minimum required for all the cases.

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Figure 4 - Roughness vs. transverse speed

Figure 5 - 3D scans of the roughened profiles of GCI (a) and A380 (b)

Figure 6 - Bond Strength vs. Average Roughness

2.1.2 Metallic alloys milling

J. Holmberg et al. [11] studied the differences between conventional milling and AWJ milling on processing gas turbines components made with superalloys (alloy 718). As a matter of fact, manufacturing of heat-resistant superalloys is heavily resource demanding (especially in last stages), hence dedicated processes have to be developed in order to improve quality and reduce costs. The authors initially performed a test campaign to study the influence of the parameters, then applied the acquired knowledge on a complex geometry similar to those found on gas turbines.

For rough machining, high pressure and low traverse speed increase the erosion depth, hence the MRR. The influence of the side step (SS) on the material removal rate (MRR) had to be investigated, and the resulting surfaces are depicted in Figure 7. The leftover material increases with increasing SS, thus the MRR will be reduced by the need of post-processing operations aimed either at improving the topography (for SS of 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm) or at removing the flange-like structures (in the case of 0.6 mm and 0.8 mm of SS).

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Figure 7 - Profile obtained with different side steps for different SSs and high jet pressure (345.6 MPa)

Regarding finishing processes, the target will be to optimize the surface characteristics. In these cases, it was found that higher SS leads to less uniform surfaces (Figure 8), while higher traverse speed leads to a more isotropic surface, lowering the surface roughness (Figure 9).

Figure 8 - Influence of SS on the resulting surface

Figure 9 - Influence of traverse speed on the resulting surface

Thanks to the accurate pre-testing campaign, the authors were able to perform successfully both roughing (pressure of 345 MPa) and finishing (pressure of 138 MPa) operations on a geometry similar to the ones employed on turbines. They chose a sidestep of 0.4 mm, which proved to be the best in terms of surface quality, and a traverse speed of 1284 mm/min. The results are shown in Figure 10 and in Table 2.

Figure 10 – Machining test using low and high pressure showing the erosion profiles.

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Method	Pressure	Time	Removed volume	MRR
<i>finishing</i>	137.9 MPa	1.355 min	0.435 cm ³	0.318 cm ³ /min
<i>roughing</i>	345.6 MPa	2.221 min	4.784 cm ³	2.154 cm ³ /min

Table 2 - Results of milling on the 'turbine-like' geometry

The most important piece of information highlighted by the authors is the need of proper programming of the tool path. Indeed, the high-pressure configuration managed to achieve a reasonable MRR of 2.154 cm³/min, but some quality issues are related to exaggerated erosion where the jet beam has changed direction. This is mainly caused by delays in the programmed path, thus suggesting need of a different approach. Improvements could be made via refined CNC programming, including variations of the jet direction, of the pressure and also of the abrasive medium.

Table 3 provides an overview of some different milling methods. Major concerns on the need of post-processing operations on 3D features milled by AWJ are related to the surface integrity after the milling operation. As a matter of fact, after impacting the workpiece, abrasive particles will fragment and embed in the material (Figure 11). Fowler G. et al. [12] estimated that, depending on the milling conditions, up to 40% of the surface area will contain embedded particles.

Parameter/ Machining Method	AWJ Milling	Rough Milling Ceramic/Cemented Carbide	Finish Milling Cemented Carbide
Ability	Cut-through, mill or post-process	Removes a certain volume in subsequent steps Often requires different setups	
Traverse/cutting speed [mm/min]	10–15	150–700	20–40
Depth of cut, rough machining [mm]	Depending on traverse speed, pressure and nozzle distance	0.7–1	0.1–0.8
MRR [cm ³ /min]	1.9–2.4	6–10	1–2
Tool requirements	No tool change	Requires tool change after 15–20 cm ³	Requires tool change after 2–4 cm ³
Others	Residue in the cut surface	Handling of chips May occur surface damages from unpredicted tool breakage Machining of small radius difficult and time consuming Could introduce detrimental stresses and deformation due to lack of cooling	
Machining geometry	Small radii, down to 0.15 mm, could be machined with same setup		

Table 3 – Comparison between rough AWJM milling and conventional milling

Figure 11 - Cross section of Ti6Al4V following AWJ milling

Impact and embedment of the particles will create compressive residual stresses on the machined surface, thus increasing the likeliness of needing subsequent machining. Both [11] and [12] were able to assess that the number of embedded particles does not depend on the number of passes; however Holmberg J. et al. [11] have shown that the residual stresses are directly proportional to the number of passes and inversely proportional to the side step (Figure 12).

Figure 12 - Surface residual stresses for different SSs and for one pass (high pressure) or two passes (high pressure pass followed by low pressure pass)

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Nevertheless, AWJ resulted to be suitable for machining cooling holes on turbomachinery blades in several experiments. H. T. Liu [3] managed to drill air breathing holes on refractory metals with and without thermal barrier (Figure 13) mounting the workpiece on a Rotary Axis and exploiting a nozzle equipped with A-Jet. Holes with inclined axis were feasible and, to a certain extent, the tilting angle and the shape of the hole could be controlled simultaneously. No damage mode was seen on the products, resulting in an optimized process since usually these kinds of holes are drilled by means of a two-step process (removal of the nonconductive thermal barrier coating, if present, by means of lasers and subsequent drilling by EDM).

Figure 13 - Shaped holes drilled by AWJ

2.1.3 Metallic alloys AWJ cutting

As it has been already highlighted, abrasive waterjet machining is one of the most promising non-conventional machining processes for difficult-to-cut materials because of the reduced mechanical and thermal damage to workpiece surfaces produced using this technique.

Kong M. C. and Axinte D. [13] have studied the response of a TiAl alloys to AWJ cutting process variables to achieve high-integrity surfaces. The effects of operating parameters (pump pressure, material removal rate, abrasive flow rate and stand-off distance) on the output process quality measures (summarized within Figure 14) have been investigated as follows:

- Geometrical accuracy is analyzed using a newly defined ‘width-to-nozzle ratio’ R_{WN} (to establish the kerf width w_i related to the nozzle diameter $W_n \Rightarrow R_{WN_i} = \frac{w_i}{W_n}$) and ‘depth-to-thickness ratio’ R_{DT} (to normalize the kerf depth of cut d_i proportional to the workpiece thickness $D_t \Rightarrow R_{DT_i} = \frac{d_i}{D_t}$) and their relationships with operating parameters.
- Homogeneity of surface texture across the cut width and its dependence on kinematic and abrasive-related parameters.
- Surface/subsurface morphology and integrity along the depth of cut are discussed to understand the mechanism of their creation.
- The ability of AWJ machining of TiAl alloys and methods to overcome possible shortcomings when applying this technique and recommendations for the possible optimal solutions are discussed.

The experiment was carried out with the setup shown in Figure 15. Operating parameters are shown in Table 4.

Figure 14 - Summary of the output measures and their investigation methods

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Figure 15 - Illustration of AWJ experimental setup

Trial group	Kinematic parameters			Abrasive-related parameters		
	Pump pressure		Material removal rate (mm ³ /min)	Abrasive flow rate		Stand-off distance (mm)
	P(psi)	P(MPa)		Valve setting	(kg/min)	
Set 1						
P1	10 000	68.95	4400	6	0.285	3
	20 000	137.9				
	30 000	206.8				
	40 000	275.8				
	50 000	344.7				
Set 2						
F1	50 000	344.7	60, 120, 150, 180, 240, 300, 450, 600, 750, 1300, 1800, 2600, 3500	6	0.285	3
Set 3						
A1	50 000	344.7	220	6 8 10	0.285 0.519 0.773	3
A2	50 000	344.7	440	6 8 9	0.285 0.519 0.650	3
A3	50 000	344.7	660	6 8 10	0.285 0.519 0.773	3
Set 4						
S1	50 000	344.7	440	6	0.285	1 3
S2	50 000	344.7	660	6	0.285	1 3
S3	50 000	344.7	220	10	0.773	1 3

Table 4 - Various operating parameters for the straight cutting experiments

After the AWJ cutting trials, the kerf width – i.e. the distance between the two cutting front walls – was inspected using an optical digital microscope (Keyence VHX3D, magnification 25x-50x) at different distances from the top surface; the surface topography of the cut samples was scanned using a roughness tester (Talysurf CLI 1000) equipped with an inductive gauge (Stylus tip radius 2 μm); roughness and waviness parameters of the surface were analysed basing on British Standards (BS EN ISO 4288:1998).

Since the kerf width and taper affect the accuracy and tolerance of parts, it is necessary to understand the characteristics of the kerf profile in terms of geometry so that manufacturers can compensate for these effects when machining components with various shapes. To evaluate the effect of the main parameters on the output process quality, Kong M.C. and Axinte D. introduced four different zones basing on the dependency of R_{WN} against R_{DT} :

- ZONE 1: $R_{WNI} > 1$; instantaneous kerf width is larger than nozzle diameter.
- ZONE 2: $R_{WNI} = 1$; instantaneous kerf width is equal to the nozzle diameter.
- ZONE 3: $R_{WNI} < 1$; instantaneous kerf width is smaller than the nozzle diameter.
- ZONE 4: $R_{WNI} = 0$; instantaneous kerf width is equal to zero revealing the fact that the workpiece has not been penetrated.

Considering the measurements reported in Figure 16, it is possible to assess that the degree of jet penetration is sensitive to pump pressure as the curves drop sharply in zone 4. An increasing pump pressure gives rise to more penetration of the cut. The results of set 1 showed that non-through cuts were obtained when the pressure was between 10 and 40 kpsi. Although at 50 kpsi through cuts were achieved, the kerf geometrical accuracy was not acceptable. Figure 17 shows the effect of changing MRR from 60 mm^3/min to 1800 mm^3/min on the kerf profile generated by AWJ cutting while keeping constant the other parameters. Figure 18 shows that the SOD has less influence on the width of the bottom kerf than on the one of the top kerf due to the difference in energy.

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Figure 16 - Distribution of R_{WN} against R_{DT} at various P .
 MRR = 4400 mm³/min, AFVS = 6, SOD = 3 mm. Set 1 trials

Figure 17 - Distribution of R_{WN} against R_{DT} at various MRR.
 $P = 50$ kpsi, AFVS = 6, SOD = 3 mm. Set 2 trials

Figure 18 - Distribution of R_{WN} against R_{DT} with various SOD.

$P = 50$ kpsi, $AFVS = 6$, $MRR=440$ mm³/min in group S2,
 220 mm³/min and $AFVS=10$ in group S3- set 4

In conclusion, although the literature concerning AWJ mainly stands that there are no problems regarding temperature, in the experiment conducted by Kong M. C. and Axinte D. it's possible to observe bubble-like protrusions attached to the workpiece surfaces. This phenomenon is most likely caused by the strong exothermic reaction that takes place between titanium and oxygen, which are present in high percentage in Ti-Al alloys.

Improvements of the cutting quality on metallic alloys can be obtained by developing more complex strategies, as showed by Xiong J. et al. [14] on samples of Ti6Al4V. The authors investigated a new strategy consisting in cutting twice the same part of the workpiece with changing the traverse direction and SOD during second cutting; depending on whether the piece was cut through during the first pass or not, the strategy was named respectively reverse trimming cutting or reverse deepening cutting. Kerf width was then analysed, measuring Ra and Sa (i.e. the arithmetic average height of the surface, introduced due to the non-uniformity of the cross-section after cutting).

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Figure 19 - Ra and Sa vs. SOD of the second pass

In Figure 19, the control group consists of a specimen cut in one pass, with a SOD of 6mm and a traverse speed of 600 mm/min. The red solid lines and the orange boxes – which represent the improvement percentage with respect to the control group – are referred to reverse trimming cutting (carried out at the same traverse speed of the control group). The blue solid lines and the blue boxes are referred to reverse deepening cutting: the two passes were carried out at a traverse speed of 1200 mm/min (so that the required time is the same with respect to the control group) hence the material was not completely pierced after the first pass. In this latter way surface quality was depleted with respect to reverse trimming cutting due to upwards deflection of the jet, which caused irregular pits at the kerf wall.

The reverse trimming cutting achieved improvements up to 62.8% on Ra and up to 73.1% on Sa (with respect to the single pass cut), obtained for an SOD of 6 mm during the first pass and of 8 mm during the second pass. Results for reverse deepening cutting are more relevant since the processing time is the same of the control group; in this case the best improvements are shown for a SOD of 6 mm during the first pass and of 4 mm during the second pass, achieving values of Ra and Sa of 51.7% and 14.9% respectively when compared to the control group.

Some improvement on the kerf taper was also observed. Reverse trimming operations showed optimal improvement by 26.1% for a SOD of 2 mm during the second pass, while reverse deepening operations showed a maximum improvement of 20.2% for a SOD during the second pass of 4 mm.

Figure 20 - Kerf taper vs. SOD of the second pass

Summarizing, the research was useful in assessing that:

- For reverse trimming processes improved surface quality was obtained for increased SOD during the second pass, while kerf taper was reduced by reducing SOD.
- For reverse deepening cutting improved surface quality was obtained for decreased SOD, while kerf taper was improved by reducing SOD.

The different trends in the quality are well explained by considering both the divergence of the jet – that increases with increasing SOD – and the momentum achieved by the abrasive particles, which increases with SOD up to a certain value where the momentum of the particles will start to decrease due to friction with air.

2.2 Composite materials

2.2.1 CFRP Machining

Fiber-reinforced composites can be classified according to the matrix type: fiber-reinforced polymer matrix (e.g. CFRP, carbon fiber reinforced plastics), fiber-reinforced metal matrix and fiber-reinforced ceramic matrix. Moreover, they can be distinguished basing on the type of fiber, which can be

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either discontinuous or continuous. In this latter case, fibers may be unidirectional, bidirectional or woven [15]-[16].

To be suitable in aerospace and automotive applications, proper machining must be feasible according to the industry standards. A typical example is the need of riveting holes to allow coupling with other parts, which usually implies a high number of holes with great quality, in order not to affect the expected mechanical performances. When using traditional processes on fiber-reinforced materials, severe tool wear can be noticed, due to the high hardness of the composite. The most important issues are however concerned with damages of the workpiece caused by the extreme non-uniformity, anisotropy and layered structure of this kind of material. Typical damage modes include delamination of the exit plane, cracks, cavities, matrix degradation and fiber pull-out [14] [17].

Montesano et al. [18] investigated experimentally the difference between conventional drilling (CD) and abrasive waterjet drilling (AWJD) when machining woven CFRP. Given the lack of studies regarding multi-directional composites, their research assumes a remarkable importance, especially in the aeronautic field. For the purpose two distinct CFRP composites were considered: AGP370-5H and SGP370-8H/8552, in form of 2.7 mm thick plates. Holes ($\text{Ø}5.1\pm0.04$ mm, commonly used in aerospace applications) were drilled either by CD or by AWJD.

AWJ used #80 mesh and 90° of incident angle with a pressure of 380 MPa (the maximum allowed by the machine) and a standoff distance of 1.5 mm; the latter two parameters were chosen basing on a preliminary analysis that resulted in better surface quality with increasing pressure and decreasing standoff distance. This is consistent with the results found by Thirumalai Kumaran S. et al. [19] who stated that a higher jet pressure, a lower standoff distance, and a lower traverse speed result in a better surface quality of the holes. CD used uncoated brad-point carbide drill bits with a spindle speed of 1000 rpm and a feed rate of 0.125 mm/rev (which again resulted in the best surface quality during a preliminary analysis). Drill bits were used for no more than 20 holes each, so that tool wear influence could be neglected.

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Table 5 shows measured roughness for the various samples. Holes made by conventional drilling on 5HS presented roughness values between 15% and 25% higher than 8HS drilled samples due to larger fiber yarns which promote more matrix fallout. Samples drilled by AWJ presented higher roughness values with respect to CD; however, the values were consistent regardless of the material, thus indicating independence from the orientation of the fiber.

Sample	R_a (μm)	R_z (μm)	R_q (μm)
5HS-CD	1.34	8.38	1.73
8HS-CD	1.16	6,81	1,32
5HS-AWJD	1.95	10.25	2.48
8HS-AWJD	1.85	10.31	2.51

Table 5 - Roughness values characterizing Abrasive Water Jet Drilling vs Conventional Drilling

Using CD, both 5HS and 8HS contained cavities caused by fiber pullout and matrix fallout due to the relative angle between the cutting tool edge direction and the fiber orientation; damage was not homogeneously distributed through the hole, it was more evident in the weft yarns. Exit plane delamination was found in most of the CD-drilled samples. AWJ drilled holes presented streaks and craters along the direction of the jet due to the abrasive particles in the stream, but in this case no matrix fallout nor fiber pullout was visible; damages did not penetrate the material and were evenly distributed on the hole surface. All these issues are depicted in Figure 21.

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Figure 21 - SEM images of 5HS hole surface for AWJ (a) and CD (b)

By looking at the plots in Figure 22 it is evident that the static behaviour does not depend on the drilling method, as both processes resulted in plates with same static behaviour.

Figure 22 - Static stress-strain curves

Fatigue tests for a low number of loading cycles (from 5000 up to 60000) show that the endurance limit is the same for CD and AWJ samples, hence the machining process does not seem to play an important role on low-cycled fatigue. In particular, for a maximum stress below the endurance limit, the stiffness and the temperature profile are the same for all the samples; whereas if the load exceeds the endurance limit CD samples show slight stiffness degradation and temperature rise (Figure 23). This means that the additional damage caused by conventional tools does not have a relevant impact on short term fatigue performances. When a high number of fatigue cycles is applied (from 60000 up to 100000 cycles), the behaviour of the plates changes: CD causes greater temperature rise and stiffness degradation with respect to AWJ (Figure 24). This clearly shows the influence of the drilling process with respect to long-term fatigue. The explanation to this behaviour has been found to be the quicker delamination showed by CD samples, caused by the machining induced damage, which allowed cracks to expand much sooner, leading to failure.

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Figure 23 - Short-term fatigue curves

Figure 24 - Fatigue test under a maximum stress of 530 MPa

(a) normalized stiffness, (b) temperature rise

All in all, this paper allowed to understand that surface roughness is not a good parameter to assess the hole quality. Moreover, the material independence of AWJ has been proven and a better understanding of machining induced damage is provided.

2.2.2 Drilling of stacked materials

The need of advanced methods for composites machining is even enhanced when dealing with CFRP jointed with metallic alloys. The use of stacked material (Figure 25) has become a common practice in the aeronautic industry in order to obtain high strength-to-weight ratio and excellent corrosion resistance. This is achieved by making the best possible use of the high strength, fatigue resistance, stiffness and modulus of elasticity of lightweight CFRP combined with the low density and high corrosion resistance of titanium alloys [20].

Figure 25 – Cross section of CFRP/metal stack

Drilling of such materials has to be made in the stacked configuration, so that assembly errors can be reduced. However, this is a difficult task, since the difference in physical and mechanical properties makes these materials prone to damage when conventionally drilled. As a matter of fact, statistics suggest that 60% of the produced parts are rejected due to poor quality of the holes. As already introduced, the main issue with regard to these materials is the difference in properties, which causes instability during conventional machining (i.e. drilling or milling) especially in the transition zone, which is the most critical in the whole part. Different properties also lead to high interface temperature, which causes irreparable thermal damage on CFRP. Feng J. et al. [20] suggested the urge to develop suitable models that can predict the behavior at the interface, hence improving machining quality.

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Thermal technologies are also difficultly suitable for these materials due to the large HAZ that would form on the interposed metallic alloy, which would lead to a decrease in performance. On the other hand, thanks to its greater temperature control and independency on materials, AWJ seemed preferable to Alberdi A. et al. [19] who decided to evaluate its viability as substitute for machining stacks of CFRP/Ti6Al4V, also analyzing the influence of the configuration (CFRP over Ti6Al4V and vice versa). The drilling process had to be divided into two steps: an initial piercing during which the jet is kept stationary until complete penetration on the material and a second step in which the jet moves in a circular pattern. The taper angle is mostly influenced by pressure, stack configuration and transverse feed rate. While titanium showed lower taper when located in the upper part, CFRP presents the opposite behavior. Due to the low machinability index, titanium always had positive taper, while CFRP presents negative taper thanks to its higher machinability. This leads to difficult control of the angle: as a matter of fact, taper compensation by means of a five-axis machine is not effective due to the different behavior of the materials. The profile geometry strictly depends on the stack configuration, being an “X” for Ti6Al4V/CFRP or a barrel shape for CFRP/Ti6Al4V (Figure 26).

Figure 26 - Profile geometry at different pressures and nozzle diameters

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Although roughness alone is not a good indicator of the hole quality (see page 30 and following), it is important to underline that minimum roughness can be obtained, at equal process parameters, using a Ti/CFRP configuration. The papers analyze in great detail how to optimize drilling of stacked materials, but some more research should be done on how to optimize the piercing phase (which may damage the hole) as well as on the effects of the tool path in the resulting quality.

2.2.3 Influence of multi-pass cutting on kerf quality

One of the main goals of AWJ cutting of CFRP is to obtain a high-quality kerf. S. Xiao, P. Wang, H. Gao, D. Soulat [23] – similarly to what already seen in section 2.1.3 – have studied whether it is possible to further improve the cutting kerf quality without sacrifice of efficiency using a multi-pass process with changed parameters among different passes. By doing this, it is possible to notice an improvement in performance and efficiency compared to single pass cutting, particularly for thick parts. In reality, multi-pass cutting with constant parameters is the first choice even though an increase in real stand-off distance among different passes could actually lead to undesired quality of the kerf. So, thanks to the experiments carried out by S. Xiao, P. Wang, H. Gao, D. Soulat, it is possible to evaluate if the actual use of the multi-pass has the same effects in terms of cutting kerf quality but especially if an efficiency increase is achieved. This paper also shows how the workpiece response changes, in particular from the point of view of the kerf taper and of the surface quality.

To evaluate the kerf generated by a multi pass cutting, the authors provide four different plots from which it is possible to understand the main differences between multi-pass cutting with constant and changing parameters (Figure 27).

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(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 27 - Kerf taper produced by multi-pass cutting with unchanged and changed parameters (continues)

(d)

Figure 27 - Kerf taper produced by multi-pass cutting with unchanged and changed parameters

It is possible to see that multi-pass cutting with constant parameters produces the highest kerf taper without any advantages and, compared to multi-pass cutting with changed parameters, the kerf taper decreases remarkably. Moreover, kerf taper can be improved by increasing pressure at second pass cutting even with relatively high traverse speed. Meanwhile the kerf taper generated by multi-pass cutting with changed parameters is almost equal to that produced by single pass cutting. Thus, it means that appropriate parameters selected at second pass cutting could achieve the cutting quality obtained by single pass cutting relatively easy.

After the kerf taper has been evaluated the researchers showed that by changing parameters it is possible to obtain a decrease of the cutting time – so an increase of cutting efficiency – compared with control group-single-pass cutting without sacrifice of kerf taper quality (Figure 28). So, the multi-pass cutting with changed parameters could further decrease the cutting time. The efficiency can be improved by almost 13% as the condition that kerf taper produced varies in a small extent.

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Figure 28 - Cutting time and kerf taper at multi-pass cutting process

Considering surface quality, it stands that R_a is influenced by multi-pass cutting with constant and changed parameters. Figure 29 (a) shows that an increase of traverse speed and pressure could undesirably lead to unpredictable fluctuations of R_a . Considering the multi-pass cutting with changed parameters, measured R_a is generally higher than that measured with constant parameters. Hence, it is inferred that the multi-pass cutting with changed parameters does not improve the surface quality, except for increasing pressure greatly at second-pass cutting with the same traverse speed.

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Figure 29 – R_a produced by multi-pass cutting with constant and changed parameters (continues)

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Figure 29 - R_a produced by multi-pass cutting with constant and changed parameters

Notice that in this case, the multi-pass cutting with changed parameters generally does not show the advantage over with constant parameters.

Concluding: the kerf taper reduced obviously by multi-pass cutting with changed parameters (the greatest reduction is about 53% with-out sacrifice of efficiency); the efficiency also improved (appropriate transverse speed selected at different passes could improve efficiency by almost 13% within roughly identical kerf taper); the surface quality generated by changed parameters is generally worse than that obtained by constant parameters. For all these reasons, the multi-pass cutting could be used to further improve CFRP cutting quality, in which material properties including debonding strength and stiffness are enough to avoid delamination.

2.3 Soft materials

Waterjet technology is capable of offering excellent performances even working with soft materials. Compared to a thermal process – for instance laser cutting or plasma arc cutting – thermal damages in material structure, dangerous gas generation (which may be carcinogenic for some plastic materials [24]) and fire issues are obviously avoided. In addition, waterjet cut is far more flexible than traditional punch tool methods and it is also characterized by higher quality kerfs. From a technological point of view, it is possible to notice that for cutting soft materials abrasive is in general not needed ([24]–[29]). For this reason, in some applications water could be even recycled ([20], [23] - which estimates a 80 per cent of water recycling - , [25]), resulting in an improvement of the environmental impact which would have been unfeasible with abrasive water jet.

Considering automotive industry, a relevant application of this technology is the three-dimensional trimming of vehicle interior components made from soft materials. This topic is presented in section 2.3.1. Besides this, it was possible to find a certain number of papers dealing with car tyres dismantling using waterjet technology instead of traditional shredding and grinding mechanical techniques. A detailed description of the problem is provided within section 2.3.2.

2.3.1 Waterjet cut of car interior parts and other applications

This section is mainly based on the article “The softly-softly approach of robotic waterjet cutting”, by B. Rooks [24]. This paper focuses on robot aided waterjet cutting of complex-shaped car interior parts instead of using traditional methods based on dies and punch tools.

This article states that more than 80 per cent of the European market for waterjet cutting was taken up by suppliers of internal car components to the major automotive OEMs – Original Equipment Manufacturers – such as Audi, BMW, Ford, Mercedes, Volkswagen, and Volvo. The reasons of this great diffusion are the one briefly described in the introduction: first of all, it is a process without heat generation, which could be potentially dangerous either for the component material or the surroundings. No toxic fumes are emitted as occurs with a laser and other thermal processes, which may be a problem for some plastic materials. However, waterjet cutting has the same advantages in terms of flexibility of

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other robot-aided cutting technologies, making punch tool operations not competitive from this point of view: a design modification needs only simple revisions to the program, a change-over in product is simply achieved by selection of the appropriate program, which is usually possible within a work cycle. Examples of this application are depicted in Figure 30 and in Figure 31.

Figure 30 - An ABB-IR Fourrob Cutting Box for producing car door panels and floor carpets

In addition to this, the paper remarks as flexibility is not the only advantage that waterjet cutting has over a punch press, the traditional process for producing “soft” interior trim components. The main reason of its widespread diffusion is that capital expenditures, lead-time and production costs are all lower. ABB I-R Waterjet Systems – a joint venture between ABB Flexible Automation (a world leading robot manufacturing company) and Ingersoll-Rand (an industrial pneumatic solutions provider) – said that “the capital cost of a waterjet cutting system is half the price of a punch tool, and it only takes five days to have a system up and running”.

Since the article [24] was written in 2001 it is possible to argue that these figures are not reliable. However, recent innovations have surely involved more the robotics and mechatronics sector than punch tools one, making this comparison at least still valid nowadays, but probably even stronger. The same manufacturer said that contribution of waterjet cutting to part cost it was just 10 per cent compared to approximately 60 per cent for a punch tool. In addition to this, a punch tool takes months to design and it could cost up to \$1 million excluding tool cost, which obviously increases as the number of part variants increase.

Fanuc Robotics (a group of companies that provide automation products and services) compared waterjet cutting over a dedicated die-cutting solution considering a system developed for a big US supplier of automotive interior trim components to cut door panels. The key advantages of the waterjet solution were the flexibility to handle changing demand together with a 40 per cent cost reduction and a footprint 50 per cent less than a die-cutting machine, which also required a two-stage operation on each panel. Also, most design changes can be defined in minutes while, with a dedicated machine, at least a two-week lead-time to tool-up for a different component trim is needed. The waterjet-based station considered is shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31 – Two Fanuc M-6 robots equipped with waterjets installed at a supplier of automotive trim components

In addition to all these considerations, it is necessary to remark that traditional cutting machines suffer from knife wear, which creates both quality problems and an increase in operating costs. With a robot waterjet cell for sure there is no degrading in cutting efficiency, and even if waterjet head nozzles must be replaced their cost is not comparable to a die replacing or re-machining. These reasons have surely favored the spread of this technology even before recent robots and electronics improvements, as stands an article (Müller S., 1988 [30]) about a pilot project using waterjet cut to realize holes in Ford Sierra's plastic bumpers.

2.3.2 Car tyres dismantling

Car tyres dismantling by means of waterjet technology is a research topic which have been discussed by different universities and research groups. This state-of-the-art review mainly relies on the academic works of Bortolussi A., Careddu N., Ciccu R. (2008 [25], 2008 [26]), Ciccu R., Costa G. (2010 [27], 2012 [28])

2.3.2.1 Problem statement

Our society bases its economy and development on road transport, since the delivery of goods and services, industrial activities, public and private transport rely on motorcycles, cars, buses, trucks, tractors etc. Obviously, tyres have a limited life. Once they are replaced by new ones, they become useless and they have to be properly dismantled. The “Global Tire Recycling Market Analysis 2025” (Goldstein Market Intelligence, 2020 [31]) stands that “Every year over 1.6 billion new tyres are generated and around 1 billion of waste tyres are generated”, thus it is not hard to understand the dimension of the problem. End-of-life car tyres treatment (shredding, granulation, pulverization) is mainly performed with mechanical means, although it has several drawbacks such as high energy consumption, tool wear, low technical efficiency and poor-quality products [28]. Waterjet treatment of scrap tyres could be a possible way to recycle both rubber and wires – which tyres are made of – turning out to be an attractive perspective from both an environmental and economic point of view, since rubber demanding is increasing and natural rubber availability is slowly dwindling [25].

2.3.2.2 Worn tyres recovery options

Once a tyre has arrived at the end of its life it is possible to highlight four different tracks:

1. Landfilling.

It consists in a huge environmental problem, mainly due to tyre bulkiness (in particular when considering trucks or operating machines tyres disposal) and to their difficulty in being decomposed (residence time in landfill sites is estimated in approximately 80-100 years [32]). The advantage of this end-of-life treatment is clearly the low capital and operating cost – but for all the aforementioned reasons, landfilling and stockpiles are the least desirable option. In addition to this it may be taken into account that illegal dumping is a dangerous and widespread phenomenon. However, EU Directive N° 1999/31 [33] banned the disposal of whole or shredded car tyres in landfills.

2. Energy recovery.

Due to their considerable calorific value (between 32 and 35 MJ/Kg according to [29] and

[34], comparable to coal's one [35]) scrap tyres could be used as fuel in waste incineration plants. Clearly it does not consist in an ecologic disposal option and there are several polluting risks related to improper and illegal tyre burning.

3. Regrooving, retreading, recycling for other uses.

Regrooving extends useful tyre life but it's suitable only for truck tyres, because the distance between the base of the tread groove and the metal rib is higher. Retreading is feasible for each type of tyre, provided that they are undamaged. Other uses mainly rely on tyres insulating and damping properties for structural and shock absorbing applications, such as crash barriers or roadbases.

4. Materials recycling.

In this case secondary raw materials deriving from tyres destruction are recycled, which properties will depend on the destruction technique used. Waterjet based destruction technologies turns out to be characterized by high quality and homogeneous products, becoming attractive even from an economic point of view. Figure 32 shows a typical outcome of this process, while particle dimension distribution (Holka H, Jarzyna T, 2008 [36]) is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 32 - Typical quality of waterjet tyre disintegration products

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Figure 33 - Histogram of interval series of rubber particles dimensions

2.3.2.3 Tyre destruction with waterjet technology

The research work of Ciccu et al. [25] highlights waterjet potential in cutting rubber and expansive materials referring to the data reported in Table 6. The suitability for destroying tyres, in fact, appears evident from the value proper of rubber.

Material	Thickness (mm)	Cutting rate [mm/min]
Rubber	2	25,000
	10	10,000
	20	2,000
Plastic (PU)	2	20,000
	5	8,000
	10	3,000
Plastic materials (PTFE, PVC)	2	6,000
	5	2,000
	10	800
Plywood	2	25,000
	5	4,000
	10	500
Expanded material	10	25,000
	100	5,000

Table 6 - Performance of waterjet for cutting rubber and expansive materials

It may also be taken into account that tyres change according to the kind of vehicle they are designed for, not only as to size but also in terms of ingredients and their proportion in the blend. Characteristics and components are reported in Table 7 and in Table 8. The rubber most commonly used for car tyres is the styrene-butadiene copolymer (SBR) [25].

COMPONENTS	Proportion %	
	Car	Truck
Rubber/elastomers	48	43
Carbon black	22	21
Steel	15	27
Textile	5	--
Zinc oxide	1	2
Sulphur	1	1
Chemical additives	8	6

Table 7 - Composition of tyres

VEHICLE TYPE	WEIGHT kg
Touring cars	7.5/8.5
Family cars	11
Truck	50
Semi trailer	55/80
Farm vehicles	100

Table 8 - Characteristics of tyres

The experimental setup which Bortolussi A., Ciccu R., Careddu N. refer to consists of the following facilities [25]:

1. High pressure pump (up to 54 l/min at 250 MPa) powered by a 350 kW diesel engine.
2. Water filled tank into which the tyre was submerged.
3. Nozzle moving system:
 - a. Transverse motion parallel to the tyre rotation axis along two cylindrical guides.
 - b. Translatory motion orthogonally with respect to the tyre rotation axis.
 - c. Nozzle rotary motion.
4. Device for rotating the tyre driven by a small wheel fixed to a lateral support.
5. A screen connected to the tank for collecting the cut rubber.

The waterjet is designed to impact against the tyre surface over a width of 7 cm. The weight of the destroyed rubber was determined after collecting and drying the removed particles by means of a precision balance.

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Rotating swivel and nozzle holder head

Water jet features

Rubber cuttings collected on the screen

Strip of tread treated in two minutes

Figure 34 - Experimental setup by Bortolussi A., Careddu N., Ciccu R.

Tests were conducted keeping the following parameters constant:

- geometry configuration of the nozzles, with coplanar axes inclined at 20° with respect to the cutting nozzle head rotation axis;
- test duration (120 s);
- tyre rotation speed (17.24 rpm).

Test variables were:

- nozzle diameter;
- waterjet pressure;
- stand-off distance;
- centered or off-centered jets with respect to tyre rotation axis.

After a test was completed, the following parameters were determined:

- tyre weight;
- part of tyre destroyed;
- weight of cuttings retained by the screen.

The part of tread treated by the single two-nozzle head was a strip about 7.5 cm wide. It follows that to destroy the entire tread in two minutes were required two heads. Once the tread has been destroyed, the two sides without metal reinforcement can be treated using a conventional blade shredder. Test results are shown in Table 9:

TEST N°	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Waterjet position	Centered	Centered	Off-centered	Off-centered	Off-centered	Off-centered	Centered	Centered
Nozzle diameter [mm]	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Pressure [MPa]	168	112.6	178	128	193	138	138	193
Waterjet velocity [m/s]	580	475	597	506	621	525	525	621
Flowrate [l/min]	11.76	9.66	12.14	10.30	8.77	7.42	7.42	8.77
Hydraulic power [kW]	33.04	18.13	36.03	21.97	28.22	17.06	17.06	28.22
Weight tread treated [kg]	1.247	1.072	0.986	1.041	1.258	1.258	1.204	1.048
Weight tire destroyed [g]	450	80	540	170	540	140	160	540
% tire destroyed	36.09	7.46	54.77	16.33	42.92	11.12	13.29	51.53

Table 9 - Experimental results on waterjet tyre destroying
by Bortolussi A., Careddu N., Ciccu R.

The data obtained were interpolated to highlight the dependency of the amount of tyre destroyed (% of the original rubber weight) with the two most important operating variables, the water pressure and the total hydraulic power. Finally, an extrapolation on the trend lines was performed in order to roughly estimate process parameters needed to completely destroy a tyre within two minutes.

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The graph reported in Figure 36 shows that to completely destroy a tyre into two minutes using a 0.5 mm nozzle almost 290 MPa are required, while about 260 MPa are sufficient to achieve the same result using a 0.6 mm nozzle. As can be observed in Figure 35, to destroy the whole tyre in two minutes a cutting output power of at least 55 kW for both nozzle sizes is required.

Figure 35 - Influence of the hydraulic power on cutting performance

Figure 36 - Influence of pressure and nozzle size on cutting performance

The work by Ciccu R., Costa G., calculates the specific energy as 0.94 kJ/g [27] although this figure might have been underestimated being it roughly calculated by linear extrapolation of few scattered and distant data, not taking into account the less-than-proportional trend normally observed at increasing power. The same researchers focus also on different rubber removal mechanisms, consisting in the disintegration of rubber into fine particles by using larger nozzles, moderate pressures and the possibility

to implement a pulsed jet aiming to reduce the specific energy required (which is the most significant parameter for the economic feasibility of the technology). The mass removal rate strictly depends on the nozzle diameter and on water flowrate – which controls the area impacted by the jet – whereas jet penetration increases with pressure, making this option more suitable for cutting rather than for material removal. The performance of each of the two options was checked experimentally at almost equal power in order to put into evidence the best solution for tyre dismantling. The expected advantages were a lower capital expenditure for the waterjet system (due to the lower pressure), better system reliability and product quality, higher performances and a higher plant capacity owing to the parallel treatment of threads and shoulders. Test results are reported in Table 10 and in Table 11.

Nozzle diameter [mm]	Pressure [MPa]	Water Flowrate [l/min]	Hydraulic power [kW]	Stand-off distance [mm]	Traverse velocity [mm/min]	Advance rate [mm/min]	Cutting rate [cm ² /min]	Specific energy [kJ/cm ²]	Processing quality
2.08	80	56	75	40	1200	230	445	10.1	Fair
2.08	80	56	75	25	1200	230	480	9.4	Fair
2.08	100	62	103	25	3000	410	778	7.9	Good
2,08	100	62	103	40	3000	470	1,037	6.0	Fair

Table 10 – Test results at different cutting rates

Nozzle diameter [mm]	Pressure [MPa]	Water Flowrate [l/min]	Hydraulic power [kW]	Stand-off distance [mm]	Traverse velocity [mm/min]	Advance step [mm]	Cutting rate [cm ² /min]	Specific energy [kJ/cm ²]	Pulsation
3,00	75	108	135	60	6000	10	600	13.5	YES
3,00	90	120	180	60	6000	10	600	18.0	YES
2,08	75	55	69	30	6000	10	600	6.9	NO

Table 11 – Test results at equal cutting rate (600 cm²/min)

As Table 10 shows, the minimum specific energy is obtained raising the cutting rate beyond 1000 cm²/min, about 3 times higher than the one registered in the high pressure tests. Assuming an average thickness of 2 cm and a volumic mass of rubber around 1 g/cm³ [27], the specific energy is about 3 kJ/g . This means that the efficiency of the two different processes – which could be assumed to be the ratio between the cutting rate and the specific energy – is nearly the same, but the productivity of the process is three times higher and better quality products are obtained (Figure 32), making it more interesting

from an industrial point of view. In the end, with this technology the mass removal rate is about 120kg/h per 100 kW of power involved.

2.3.2.4 Further evolutions, economic analysis related patents

The simple equipment employed, the robustness, the great flexibility and the possibility of an highly automated process make this technology a rival for traditional tyre destruction techniques. Further studies may be performed in order to improve both process efficiency and productivity. Lastly, the authors suggest that investigation should be extended to two-nozzled rotating waterjet heads [25], [27]. By increasing the number of two-nozzled rotating waterjet heads, in fact, the rate of tyre destroyed (and hence productivity) increases proportionally, while the capital and operating costs (for pumps of increasing output as a function of number of nozzles) increase less than proportionally. A waterjet facility of this type would deliver high productivity adopting an economically efficient process to yield good quality products.

Some of the aforementioned papers ([25], [26], [27]) provide a simple economic model to support the application of this technology in a proper plant. In any case, these projects have to be considered as academic prototypes, far from a concrete and effective plant application. However, it is possible to highlight the fact that some patents about a real plant application of waterjet-based scrap tyre dismantling have been published ([37]–[39]).

2.4 Employment of WJ/AWJ in modern companies

Surfing the internet, we were able to find different industries that exploit WJ/AWJ as a machining method for metallic alloys. One of them is “Milco Waterjet”, that provides some of the most important aerospace manufacturers with many different products such as aircraft body panels, aircraft engine blades, impellers, landing gears etc. (more detailed information is available on their website, <https://milcowaterjet.com/>). “Atlantis Waterjet” (<https://atlantiswaterjet.com/index.html>) is another American company that provides waterjet cutting services for many applications, ranging from soft materials to metallic alloys. Many other companies employing waterjet are present in the market, such as

2.4 *Employment of WJ/AWJ in modern companies*

“Aerospace Metals LLC” (<https://aerospacemetalsllc.com/waterjet-cutting/>), and they have in common the fact that their customers are mainly companies active in the aerospace, automotive and defence sectors. “MERCER Gasket & Shim” (<https://mercergasket.com/>) produces gasket, shims, and components related to heat exchangers and boilers. They provide a complete equipment list which includes AWJ related facilities. In between the industries that exploit waterjet related to machine soft materials, there is “Comi Group” (<https://comispa.it/>) which sells “Cutting Box”, suitable for trimming of internal parts of the car (such as carpets, dashboards and noise insulation panels) thanks to its high automation which allows for greater production rates.

Summarizing, we can notice how the waterjet sector is really active, since several companies can be found that provide AWJ machined products, or that directly sell facilities related to this technology.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Before drawing the conclusions of this work, an overview of all contributes involved is provided. Table 12 collects all external resources and highlights relevant information (title, year of publication, authors) and some key topics (field of application, materials machined, machining features). The analysis becomes more in-depth in the following charts, focusing on publication year (Figure 37), field of application (Figure 38) and materials machined (Figure 39).

#	TITLE	YEAR	AUTHORS	APPLICATION	
				Automotive	Aerospace
1	Operational vibration of a waterjet focuser as means for monitoring its wear progression	2021	Annoni M., Copertaro E., Perotti F.	YES	YES
2	Recent Progress Trend on Abrasive Waterjet Cutting of Metallic Materials: A Review	2021	Aamir M., Milaor Llanto J., Tolouei-Rad M., Vafadar A.	YES	YES
3	"7M" Advantage of Abrasive Waterjet for Machining Advanced Materials	2017	Liu H. T.	YES	YES
4	ABRASIVE WATER JET (AWJ) APPLICATIONS IN THE AVIATION INDUSTRY	2019	Saracyakupoglu T.	NO	YES
5	APPLICATION OF ABRASIVE WATERJET FOR 3D MACHINING	2013	Liu H. T., Olsen J. H.	YES	YES
6	Boeing 787 from the ground up	2006	Hale J.	NO	YES
7	WIKIPEDIA, "CFRP Applications"	2022	-	NO	NO
8	Lightweight Aluminum Alloys in Aerospace and Automotive	2020	Spira N.	YES	YES
9	Fatigue resistance and influence of cutting technology on the mechanical properties of modern steels used in the automotive industry	2017	Nový F., Ulewicz R.	YES	NO
10	Pulsed waterjet roughening of cast iron and aluminium alloy for automotive engine remanufacturing with plasma transferred wire arc coating	2020	O'Neil N., Syed Kabir A.	NO	YES
11	Abrasive Water Jet Milling as An Efficient Manufacturing Method for Superalloy Gas Turbine Components	2022	Berglund J., Holmberg J., Wretland A.	NO	YES
12	A technical note on grit embedment following abrasive water-jet milling of a titanium alloy	2005	Fowler G., Shipway P. H., Pashby I. R.	NO	YES

Table 12 - Resources overview (continues)

3. CONCLUSIONS

#	TITLE	YEAR	AUTHORS	APPLICATION	
				Automotive	Aerospace
13	Response of titanium aluminide alloy to abrasive waterjet cutting: geometrical accuracy and surface integrity issues versus process parameters	2009	Axinte D., Kong M. C.	NO	YES
14	A New Strategy for Improving the Surface Quality of Ti6Al4V Machined by Abrasive Water Jet: Reverse Cutting with Variable Standoff Distances	2021	Xiongj J., Wan L., Quian Y., Sun S., Li D., Wu S.	NO	YES
15	Fiber-reinforced polymer composites: Manufacturing, properties, and applications,	2019	Linul E., Pagar D. D., Menezes P. L., Rajak D. K.	YES	YES
16	Damage study of fiber-reinforced composites drilled by abrasive waterjet – challenges and opportunities	2022	Zhang Y., Liu D., Zhang W., Zhu H., Huang C.	YES	YES
17	Influence of the damage generated by abrasive waterjet texturing on the tensile static and fatigue behaviour of 3D woven composite in the context of repair	2021	Coulaud M., Crouzeix L., Lamouche D., Sourd X., Zitoune R.	NO	YES
18	Influence of drilling and abrasive water jet induced damage on the performance of carbon fabric/epoxy plates with holes	2017	Bougherara H., Fawaz Z., MontesaNO J.	YES	YES
19	ANFIS modeling of surface roughness in abrasive waterjet machining of carbon fiber reinforced plastics	2017	Ko T. J., Kumaran S. T., Kurniawan R., Li C., Uthayakumar M.	YES	YES
20	A review on the drilling of CFRP/Ti stacks: Machining characteristics, damage mechanisms and suppression strategies at stack interface	2022	Bie W., Jiao F., Li Y., Niu Y., Zhang Z.	NO	YES
21	CFRP/titanium hybrid material for improving composite bolted joints	2008	Kolesnikov B., Herbeck L., Fink A.	NO	YES
22	An experimental study on abrasive waterjet cutting of CFRP/Ti6Al4V stacks for drilling operations	2016	Alberdi A., Artaza T., Girot F., Rivero A., Suárez A.	NO	YES
23	A study of abrasive waterjet multi-pass cutting on kerf quality of carbon fiber-reinforced plastics	2019	Gao H., Soulat D., Wang P., Xiao S.	YES	YES
24	The softly-softly approach of robotic waterjet cutting	2001	Rooks B.	YES	NO
25	A new technology for the disposal of worn car tires	2008	Bortolussi A., Careddu N., Ciccu R.	YES	NO

Table 12 - Resources overview (continues)

3. CONCLUSIONS

#	TITLE	YEAR	AUTHORS	APPLICATION	
				Automotive	Aerospace
26	A new technology for recycling scrap mine tires	2008	Bortolussi A., Careddu N., Ciccu R.	YES	NO
27	WATERJET DISMANTLING OF END-OF-LIFE OVERSIZE DUMPER TYRES	2010	Ciccu R., Costa G.	YES	NO
28	Recycling of secondary raw materials from end-of-life car tires	2012	Ciccu R., Costa G.	YES	NO
29	Recycling of car tires by means of Waterjet technologies	2017	Holka H., Jarzyna T.	YES	NO
30	Robots optimise waterjet cutting at Ford Genk	1988	Mueller S.	YES	NO
31	Global Tire Recycling Market Analysis 2025: Opportunity, Demand, Growth And Forecast 2017-2025	2020	Goldstein Market intelligence	YES	NO
32	Directions for material recovery of used tires and their use in the production of new products intended for the industry of civil construction and pavements	2018	Bulei C., Heput T., Kiss I., Todor M. P.	YES	NO
33	Council directive 1999/31/EC on the landfill of waste	1999	Council of the European Union	YES	NO
34	Energy recover from tyres waste through thermal option	2012	Dal Maschio R., Ischia M., Panaitescu V.N., Rada E. C., Ragazzi M.	YES	NO
35	Fuels - Higher and Lower Calorific Values.	-	Engineering ToolBox	NO	NO
36	Analysis of innovative methods for car tire comminution	2016	Holka H., Jarzyna T.	YES	NO
37	The disintegration of rubber tyres using ultra high pressure fluid jets	2003	Blair D.	YES	NO
38	Equipment for controllable fine milling of tires and other elastic materials with ultra-high pressure liquid jet process	2009	Moldovan G.	YES	NO
39	Plant for recycling tires	2011	Verri R.	YES	NO

Table 12 - Resources overview (continues)

3. CONCLUSIONS

#	MATERIAL				TECHNOLOGY			
	Metallic Alloys	Composites	Soft Materials	Other	Cutting	Drilling	Milling	Surface treatment
1	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
2	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
3	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
4	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
5	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO
6	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
7	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
8	YES	NO	NO	NO	-	-	-	-
9	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
10	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES
11	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
12	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
13	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
14	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
15	YES	YES	NO	NO	-	-	-	-
16	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
17	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
18	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
19	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO
20	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
21	YES	YES	NO	NO	-	-	-	-
22	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
23	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
24	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
25	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
26	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO

Table 12 - Resources overview (continues)

3. CONCLUSIONS

#	MATERIAL				TECHNOLOGY			
	Metallic Alloys	Composites	Soft Materials	Other	Cutting	Drilling	Milling	Surface treatment
27	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
28	NO	NO	YES	NO	-	-	-	-
29	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
30	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
31	-	-	YES	-	-	-	-	-
32	NO	NO	YES	NO	-	-	-	-
33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
36	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
37	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
38	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
39	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO

Table 12 - Resources overview

Figure 37 - Papers distribution by publication year

3. CONCLUSIONS

Papers distribution by field of application

Figure 38 - Papers distribution by field of application

Papers distribution by material

Figure 39 - Papers distribution by material

3. CONCLUSIONS

With respect to machining of metals, in particular highly resistant alloys, we can conclude that AWJ is particularly suitable for features with “high in-plane geometry”. It has benefits over conventional machining when dealing with small features with restricted tool access, which may be difficult to be supplied with lubricants and coolants. Moreover, the absence of thermal interaction allows to use AWJ machining wherever modifications of the microstructure are not acceptable. Great benefits could be provided by extending CNC control on more process parameters so that idle times between the roughing and the finishing phase can be almost completely removed. These characteristics, combined with the material independence of AWJ, make this technology particularly suitable for the aerospace industry which is in continuous need of lighter and more performing materials machined with really high quality.

Despite the huge amount of research, MRR is still a critical point for this technology, with few room for improvements. This is why application of WJ and AWJ in the automotive field remains constrained to the cutting of soft materials needed for car interiors, since its employment on metals would not allow for the high production volumes of this industry. Improvements may be achieved by means of rotating heads equipped with multiple nozzles, but the scarce amount of research on this topic did not allow for a meaningful analysis.

As regards soft material cutting, waterjet technology has been used for a long time and it has substantially reached the top of its evolution, at least considering the cutting architecture itself. Further developments may provide an even greater flexibility and a higher automation level by the adoption of high-performance robots, but these improvements are mainly related to mechatronics and electronics fields rather than the manufacturing one. As for car tyres dismantling, the considerable number of academic papers in respect of that does not really find a market feedback. Considering publication years it is possible to argue that it is not a trending topic for the current industrial scenario, although this trend may change considering today’s environmental needs. For sure, a plant capable of dismantling both the rim and the tyre would be a fascinating solution but it was not possible to find information about the existence of projects or papers about that.

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